

VALUES EDUCATION AND HUMAN BEHAVIOUR

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Paper Received On: 21 JUNE 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 30 JUNE 2023

Published On: 01 JULY 2023

Abstract

Moral education had been a concern for centuries in Indian Education system. Down the ages, India was honored as Vishv Guru because of its strong value system. But with the passage of time values are drying up in the Indian society to an abysmal low. This paper tries to explore the condition of value education in Himachal Pradesh, and introduction of value education. Value Education tries to introduce students with the concept of values, its classification, and methods of inculcation of values. Though values are taught as a value; but the need of the hour is to introduce more chapters on practical and theoretical aspects of values. As the problems of depression, delineation, violence at family, society and national and international level are increasing, day by day; it the duty of the Higher Education Institutions to armor their graduates with the weapon of values. Values are very important aspect of human behaviour. If an individual is not possess values, he/she cannot use all his/her full potentialities and perform his/her duties. Further, this affects others in many forms, like conflicts at personal and interpersonal levels, unhealthy social relations at personal and interpersonal level, many kinds of psychosomatic diseases and unhealthy behavioural patterns. For a better future, it is the need of the hour to equip our students or future citizens with values.

Keywords: Value education, peace, higher education.

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Introduction

In this age of unprecedented violence: locally, nationally, and globally, it is a serious matter that educational institutions, which are meant to be the nurseries of peace, have become transmission points for violence. Our country has a great and glorious tradition and history of values. Yes, only a great tradition and history of values; because we all are familiar with the state of value degradation in the contemporary times. Values are depleting at such a fast speed that, the day will soon arrive values will become a thing of the past. Indian society is facing values crisis, which were never witnessed in the history.

After witnessing a remarkable value erosion in the west, our thinkers and educational planners have introduced on value education in many states. Our state is one of those states, where value education has been introduced at many levels; starting from school and at some college courses. And B. Ed course is one of them. We are teaching values in B.Ed course, entitled as “Development of self”. In Himachal Pradesh, Value Education tries to introduce students with the concept of values, its classification, sources of values and methods of inculcation of values.

Something is better than nothing. But this is not enough, to check the erosion of values and for the inculcation of values. Once I was talking to one of my very senior colleagues about the failure of this paper to inculcate values among future teachers. He questioned- where is this written that we should inculcate values among our students? We are expected to teach them- what is truth? What is non-violence? What is love? But there are no provisions to evaluate

whether the values have been inculcated or not inculcated among the students. The result is that

for some of the students, this paper is only meant for cramming the facts, vomiting in the papers. They cram the facts to pass paper, sometimes even use unfair means for this purpose. There are many incidents of cheating in examinations in the paper of values. And once a shocking incidence was reported- a future teacher was caught in the examinations coping from a chit. More shocking part of the incidence was: he was writing the definition of truth from the chit (Chandel, 2016). This was just a minute example of the failure of our curriculum, to inculcate values among students. And, in general one can read in the newspapers; the list of undesirable and antisocial behavior committed by the teachers, like money embezzlement, rapes, drinking in schools, beating of children etc. This is the condition, where values are taught.

Let us take a glimpse of premier institutions of India. In newspapers and magazines we generally read the about the deteriorating mental and emotional health of the students. The situation is becoming alarming day by day. In India Today dated 14th September 2011 issue, a news about IITS, one of India’s premier institutes, was published. It says “...The premier institutes have been plagued by a number of problems.... So far seven students from the IITs have ended their lives this year alone. Rising stress levels and cases of depression are taking a toll on the IITians.” Seven suicides in a single year. One can imagine the graveness of the problem. A research on “Depression and type D Personality among undergraduate medical

students” was conducted by Som Gupta and Prosenjit Basak. They concluded: “Prevalence rate of depression was 45.3%,

which was mostly of mild type (34%)”. This is condition of mental health of future doctors. At this point of time, another research by Dr. Nitin Joseph on “Prevalence of depression among pre-university college students in an urban area of South India” is worth mentioning. The findings of this research exposed a very dismal picture. This study was reported on 308 students. Out of which, 79.2% were suffering from depression. Among these 41.2% were suffering from moderate depression and rest with moderate and mild depression. “Prevalence of depression ($P=0.027$) and severity of depression ($P=0.0357$) was found to significantly increase with age of the participants.” This study stressed the need for college students to be educated about depression in order to improve recognition and diagnosis. Also student counseling service offering mental health assistance needs to be established at colleges.

After witnessing this dismal picture of the mental conditions of the future doctors, engineers and other responsible citizens; the question arise, after so much meticulous planning, where are we lacking? What is the deficiency in our education system? There is the need of introspection at this point. Brilliant students who can crack the entrance examinations of IIT’s and medical colleges, are not able to control or manage their emotions. Now, what are these emotions? The word emotion originate from the Latin root word: ‘*emovere*’, which means to stir up or excite (Concise Oxford Dictionary). Love, anger, hate, fear are some of the strong emotions. Emotions disturb the peaceful state of a person, the balance of mind of a person. Peace is the state of mind when there is no disturbance by emotions. If the emotions of a person are in balance, the person will at an equilibrium state with himself/herself. And if this equilibrium is disturbed, the peace is lost. If this equilibrium is maintained, the individual is at peace with himself/herself. He can think properly, endure the ups and downs of life and can act in a balanced way. If an individual

is not at peace with oneself, he/she cannot use all his/her full potentialities and perform his/her duties. Further, this affects others in many forms, like conflicts at personal and interpersonal levels, unhealthy social relations at personal and interpersonal level, many kinds of psychosomatic diseases and unhealthy behavioural patterns. So the need of the hour is introduction of value education with special focus on peace education. Peace education is an integral part of value education. Moral values and peace education had been a concern for centuries in Indian Education system. Down the ages, India was honoured as Vishv Guru because of it’s strong value system. But with the passage of time values are drying up in the

Indian society to an abysmal low. This is a matter of shame for all of us. Hundreds of papers try to explore the condition of value education, everyone gives his/her own point of view. In Himachal Pradesh, also many such type of activities are performed. But need of the hour is a strong value education system. Peace Education as a major component of value education.

Though peace is taught as one of the universal values ; but the need of the hour is to introduce more chapters on practical and theoretical aspects of peace. As the problems of depression, delinquency, violence at family, society and national and international level are increasing, day by day; it is the duty of the Higher Education Institutions to armor their graduates with the weapon of peace. Peace is one of the universal values preached by all the religions. Peace is a very important aspect of human behaviour and value system. The importance of peace increases manifold because it is related to emotional aspect of human personality. Peace is the state of mental equipoise, a complete tensionlessness, which is referred as 'Sthitprajana' a state of unwavering mind which Maharshi Patanjali calls (*Chitta Vritti Nirodha*).Peace means liberation of

mind from all the emotions like: love, hatred, fear, anger etc. There are many levels of peace. At the lowest end peace begins with absence of physical violence, followed by violence by words, lastly violence by thoughts. Emotions play a very important role in maintaining or disturbing the peace.

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